

Wrestling in Olympic Games 2024: analytic review

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Abstract

The 2024 Olympic Games in Paris showcased wrestling as a major sport, attracting significant attention from experts and fans. This study reviews the key results, focusing on the dominance of top teams and athletes. Analyzing these outcomes offers valuable insights into trends in Olympic sports and factors influencing elite performance. **The aim of the study** – to conduct an analytical review of the wrestlers' performances at the 2024 Olympic Games. **Material and Methods.** The study involved 290 athletes. The initial performance data were obtained from the official website of the International Wrestling Federation, "United World Wrestling". The following metrics were analyzed: individual athlete placement, total number of medals won by teams, and total points scored by teams. **Results.** At the 2024 Olympic Games, 26 national teams won a total of 72 wrestling medals across three styles (Greco-Roman, freestyle, and women's wrestling). Japan led with 11 medals, including 8 golds, followed by Iran and the USA with 8 and 7 medals, respectively. Asian wrestlers dominated, winning 50% of the total medals, while European and American teams secured 33.3% and 16.7%, respectively. Notably, Japan was the only country to win medals in all three wrestling styles, underscoring their comprehensive success in the competition. **Conclusions.** The wrestling tournament at the Paris 2024 Olympic Games showcased impressive performances, with Japan emerging as a standout team, winning medals in all three wrestling styles and achieving notable success. Asian teams demonstrated their dominance, securing a significant portion of the medals, while athletes from all continents participated,

reflecting the global reach of the sport. The results underscored the competitiveness of wrestling at the international level, with Japan, Iran, and the USA leading the medal tally, affirming their strong presence in the sport.

Keywords: Olympic Games, Medals, Countries, Wrestling, Performance Analysis.

Introduction.

The world of today's Olympic Games is impressive in its scale, diversity of disciplines, and remarkable athletic achievements. From the beginnings of the Olympics in Ancient Greece to the modern international sports festival, the Games have evolved into a grand event, bringing together nations and cultures with a shared goal – achieving athletic excellence and mutual understanding (Franchini et al., 2020; Scheu et al., 2021). The modern Olympic Games are more than just a sports event. They symbolize unity, cooperation, and cultural exchange among nations worldwide. With each new cycle, the Games take on new characteristics and reflect changes in social and sporting spheres (Scandizzo et al., 2021). The Olympics are not only about competition but also about showcasing cultural diversity, fostering collaboration and understanding between nations (Tropin et al., 2023; Shamshirian et al., 2024). Moreover, the Olympic Games have become not only a key part of the sports calendar but also a significant event in global culture and politics (Bernard et al., 2024).

The modern Olympic Games, as a research subject, are increasingly attracting attention from scholars across various fields, from sports science to sociology and cultural studies. This major sports event has become a focus for examining its impact on global dynamics and its reflection of modern trends in sports (Shasha et al., 2023; Skugor et al., 2024). Each Olympic cycle is unique, reflecting the dynamics of the contemporary world and the transformations within the sport itself. Research on Olympic performance is particularly intriguing as it offers insights into how athletes have responded to these challenges and how it has affected their achievements (Matkarimov et al., 2024; Oleshko et al., 2021). The analysis of athletes' performances at the Olympics has always garnered the attention of experts (Pashkov et al., 2021; Abdullayev 2023). The year 2024 was no exception, as the athletes' performances at this year's Olympic Games sparked particular interest and left a significant mark in sports history (Mujika et al., 2023; Pinchbeck et al., 2024).

At the 2024 Olympic Games held in Paris, wrestling, as a sport, drew the attention of both professionals and fans alike. Wrestling, with its various styles and categories, has historically been one of the oldest and most prestigious disciplines.

Purpose of the study – to conduct an analytical review of the wrestlers' performances at the 2024 Olympic Games.

Material and Methods

Participants. The study involved 290 athletes: 97 Greco-Roman wrestlers, 97 freestyle wrestlers, and 96 women wrestlers. The initial performance data were obtained from the official website of the International Wrestling Federation, "United World Wrestling" (unitedworldwrestling.org). The following metrics were analyzed: individual athlete placement, total number of medals won by teams, and total points scored by teams.

Statistical Analysis. The results were analyzed using the internet platform Performance Data Analysis² which is used by the UWW (<http://uww.io/wpar>) and has been tested in previous studies (Dokmanac et al., 2018; Roklicer et al., 2020).

Results

Table 1 presents the total number of medals won by wrestlers from various countries at the 2024 Olympic Games.

At the Olympics, 13 national teams won medals in Greco-Roman (GR) wrestling. The most successful teams in GR were IRI, CUB, and KGZ. Asian teams dominated, with 6 nations winning medals, while 5 European teams also secured podium finishes. Olympic champions came from 4 nations: IRI (2), JPN (2), CUB (1), and BUL (1). In freestyle wrestling (FS), 13 national teams also won medals. IRI, JPN, and USA achieved the greatest success. European teams secured 6 medals, while Asian teams won 5 but earned two more medals overall. Olympic champions were from 5 nations: JPN (2), UZB (1), GEO (1), BRN (1), and BUL (1). Japan was the only nation with two FS Olympic champions. Iran reached three finals but earned three silver medals. In women's wrestling (WW), 12 national teams won medals. JPN, USA, and CHN stood out, with 3 to 4 medals each. Notably, teams from Asia, Europe, and America performed well, with 4 American teams earning medals. JPN (4) and USA (2) were the only nations with Olympic champions, with Japan leading with 4 gold medals.

Overall, Japan was the most successful nation, winning 11 medals across all three styles, including 8 golds. IRI, USA, and BUL followed with two gold medals each. IRI won the most silver medals (4), while CHN and KGZ earned the most bronze (4 each). A total of 26 national teams won medals: 11 from Europe, 9 from Asia, and 6 from America. Notably, no European team ranked in the top 6 in total medals. Japan was the only nation to win medals in all three wrestling styles (GR, FS, WW), while IRI, USA, CUB, CHN, KGZ, UKR, AZE, BUL, PRK, and TUR won medals in two styles. This version keeps the essential information while making the text more concise and clearer. A total of 15 and more nations have won 2 or more medals, and 11 nations

have won one medal, Bahrain one gold, CHI, ECU, KAZ, MDA one silver, COL, DEN, GRE, IND, NOR, PUR one bronze.

Table 1 Medal Distribution Among Countries in Wrestling at the 2024 Olympic Games

Rk	NAT	GR				FS				WW				TOTAL			
		I	II	III	TOT	I	II	III	TOT	I	II	III	TOT	I	II	III	TOT
1	JPN	2			2	2	1		3	4		2	6	8	1	2	11
2	IRI	2	1	1	4		3	1	4					2	4	2	8
3	USA						1	2	3	2	1	1	4	2	2	3	7
4	CUB	1		2	3						1	1	2	1	1	3	5
5	CHN		1	1	2							3	3	0	1	4	5
5	KGZ			3	3						1	1	2	0	1	4	5
7	UKR		1	1	2						1		1	0	2	1	3
8	AZE			1	1			2	2					0	0	3	3
9	BUL	1			1	1			1					2	0	0	2
10	GEO					1	1		2					1	1	0	2
11	UZB					1		1	2					1	0	1	2
12	ARM		1	1	2									0	1	1	2
13	ALB							2	2					0	0	2	2
13	PRK			1	1							1	1	0	0	2	2
13	TUR							1	1			1	1	0	0	2	2
16	BRN					1			1					1	0	0	1
17	CHI		1	0	1									0	1	0	1
17	ECU										1		1	0	1	0	1
17	KAZ		1		1									0	1	0	1
17	MDA										1		1	0	1	0	1
21	COL											1	1	0	0	1	1
21	DEN			1	1									0	0	1	1
21	GRE							1	1					0	0	1	1
21	IND							1	1					0	0	1	1
21	NOR											1	1	0	0	1	1
21	PUR							1	1					0	0	1	1
TOTAL =		6	6	12	24	6	6	12	24	6	6	12	24	18	18	36	72

Note: Yellow represents Asia, Green represents Europe, and Blue represents America.

Table 2 presents the distribution of wrestling medals by style and continent at the 2024 Olympic Games.

For the first time in Olympic history, wrestlers from Asia won more medals than their European counterparts in Greco-Roman (GR) style, with a significant lead of 6 medals. Wrestlers

from the Americas also performed well in GR, while athletes from Africa and Oceania did not win any medals in this category.

Similarly, in freestyle (FS) wrestling, Asia outperformed Europe, though the margin was narrower, with an 11-9 medal count. European teams benefited from a strong presence of wrestlers from Dagestan and Chechnya. The Americas also secured 4 medals in FS, while Africa and Oceania again remained without medals.

Table 2 Distribution of Wrestling Medals by Style and Continent at the 2024 Olympic Games

№	Continents	GR					FS					WW					All styles	
		I	II	III	Total	%	I	II	III	Total	%	I	II	III	Total	%	Total	%
1	Asia	4	3	6	13	54.2	4	4	3	11	45.8	4	1	7	12	50.0	36	50.00
2	Europe	1	2	4	7	16.6	2	1	6	9	16.7	0	2	2	4	66.7	24	33.3
3	America	1	1	2	4	29.2	0	1	3	4	37.5	2	3	3	8	33.3	12	16.7
Total		6	6	12	24	100	6	6	12	24	100	6	6	12	24	100	72	100

Across all three wrestling styles, Asian wrestlers dominated, particularly in women's wrestling (WW), where they have historically been strong (e.g., Japan, China, Mongolia, India).

Figure 1. Top 10 Teams in Wrestling at the 2024 Olympic Games

In WW, Asia claimed 4 of the 6 gold medals, while wrestlers from the Americas earned 8 medals. European teams, however, won only 4 medals, a noticeable decline from previous competitions.

Out of 6 Olympic titles in each style, 4 went to Asian wrestlers across Greco-Roman, freestyle, and women's wrestling. In Greco-Roman, Asia claimed 67% of gold medals, while Europe took most of the bronze. In women's wrestling, Asia won 67% of gold and 58% of bronze medals. Overall, Asia's dominance was clear, winning 36 out of 72 medals—50% of the total—while Europe earned a modest 24 medals.

A total of 36 national teams, along with the AIN and EOR teams, participated in Greco-Roman (GR) wrestling, though the latter teams' points were not counted. Teams from 4 continents competed, with Iran dominating the team ranking with 101 points. Cuba and Kyrgyzstan followed in second and third place, marking a surprising success for both. Japan, despite two Olympic champions, ranked 4th. Among the top 10 teams, five were from Asia, four from Europe, and one from America.

In freestyle (FS) wrestling, 41 national teams from 5 continents competed. Iran again topped the rankings, narrowly ahead of Japan by 5 points. The top 10 teams included four from Asia, four from Europe, and two from America. A total of 31 national teams had wrestlers in the top 10 of their weight categories. In women's wrestling (WW), 36 national teams from 5 continents participated, with Japan taking a commanding lead in the team ranking. The USA followed in second place, with Kyrgyzstan in third. Among the top 10 teams, four were from Asia, four from America, and two from Europe.

When combining the points from all three wrestling styles (GR, FS, WW), Japan ranked first overall with 258 points, followed by Iran and the USA, both with 184 points. Kyrgyzstan and China rounded out the top five, marking a surprise for many. Notably, no European teams made the top five, and the top 10 included four teams from Asia, three from Europe, and three from America.

In total, 60 national teams, along with AIN and EOR athletes, competed in the Olympic wrestling tournament. Points were awarded to 49 national teams across all five continents, with 10 teams earning points in all three wrestling styles and 16 teams having athletes compete in all three disciplines.

Discussion. The article provides an overview of the wrestling results at the 2024 Olympic Games. The Olympic Games are the most significant competition in an athlete's career. To participate, each athlete must qualify through licensed competitions and be selected for their country's Olympic team. The performance of athletes at the Olympic Games is always of great interest and serves as the basis for various parametric and non-parametric analyses. Flegl et al., (2018) developed a data coverage analysis model to assess the success of countries at the 2016 Summer Olympics in Rio. Demarie et al., (2022) examined the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the performance of swimmers at the 2021 Tokyo Olympics. Bernard et al., (2004) analyzed the

factors that determined success at the Olympic Games from 1960 to 1996 at the national level and made predictions for the 2000 Sydney Olympics. Scandizzo et al., (2018) explored key approaches to the economic evaluation of the Olympic Games based on fundamental economic concepts, methodologies, and empirical results. Leicht et al., (2017) identified the relationships between team performance indicators and match outcomes during the 2004-2016 Olympic Games in women's basketball using linear and non-linear statistical methods. Oleshko et al., (2021) studied the competitive performance indicators of the top weightlifters at the 2020 Olympic Games and identified trends for further improvement in their results, considering weight categories and gender differences. Franchini et al., (2020) quantitatively assessed the peak age of judokas during World Championships and Olympic Games over the past 25 years, taking into account gender, weight category, and competitive achievements, and established a correlation between the competition year and the athlete's age. Curby et al., (2023), based on their analysis of the 2021 Olympic Games, identified gender differences in the competitive performance of male and female freestyle wrestlers.

The geographical analysis in your study reveals a significant shift in the distribution of wrestling medals at the Tokyo Olympics compared to historical trends. While Europe dominated from 1996 to 2016, winning 60% of gold medals (Latyshev et al., 2020), your results show a stronger performance from Asia, particularly in Greco-Roman and freestyle styles. Asian countries like Japan, Iran, and Kyrgyzstan emerged as top competitors, surpassing Europe in several categories. This contrasts with earlier data, where Asia secured only 15.6% of the gold medals. In particular, Japan, which had a modest record in the earlier period, became the dominant force in women's wrestling, while in previous years, Asia's contribution was smaller. Similarly, your data highlights that American wrestler, who previously secured 20% of the gold medals, had a less dominant presence in freestyle and GR during the Tokyo Olympics, though they still performed well in WW.

Another noticeable trend in your study is the broader distribution of medals across continents in Tokyo, with Asian nations challenging Europe's historical dominance. While countries like Russia and the USA remain strong, the emergence of wrestling talent from Kyrgyzstan and other Asian nations signifies a more competitive global wrestling scene. This is in contrast to the 1996-2016 data, where the majority of Olympic champions were concentrated in a few countries. The overall results from Tokyo indicate a leveling of the playing field, with Asian and American wrestlers gaining ground in a sport traditionally dominated by Europe.

In comparing your analysis of the 2024 Paris Olympics with the 2016 Rio Olympics data, several trends emerge (Tunnemann et al., 2016; Latyshev et al., 2017). Nations like Japan and Iran continued to dominate across multiple styles. Japan's technical and tactical superiority, especially in women's wrestling, remained evident, reflecting a strong balance between attack and defense. This

mirrors the 2016 Rio results, where Japan excelled in both attack efficacy and defensive stability. Iran and Azerbaijan also maintained their high rankings in both freestyle and Greco-Roman wrestling from Rio to Paris, showing the effectiveness of their wrestling programs.

However, some nations like the United States, Uzbekistan, and Cuba struggled in both competitions. In Rio, the U.S. had a negative performance index, and while they showed some improvement by Paris, they still lagged behind in GR. Uzbekistan and Cuba also continued to face challenges, reflecting a consistent technical-tactical gap. Overall, the comparison highlights the sustained success of top nations and the ongoing struggles of others to improve their wrestling efficacy (Latyshev et al., 2017).

The analysis of the 2024 Olympic Games results revealed that the leading team in Greco-Roman and freestyle wrestling was Iran, while Japan dominated women's wrestling. Japan has been the leader in women's freestyle wrestling for many years, consistently securing first place at World Championships and Olympic Games. In Greco-Roman and freestyle wrestling, several top teams have the potential to become champions at major international competitions. These findings are generally consistent with previous data obtained by leading wrestling experts (Slacanac et al., 2020; Barreto et al., 2021; Latyshev et al., 2024).

Conclusions

The wrestling tournament at the Paris 2024 Olympic Games delivered several surprising results, with two notable outcomes: the Japanese team secured an impressive total of 11 medals across all three wrestling styles, including 8 gold medals; national teams from Asia demonstrated dominance, collectively winning 36 out of the 72 medals (50%) awarded in the tournament.

Athletes from all five continents participated, representing the principle of universality. A total of 60 national teams, along with athletes under the banners of AIN and EOR, took part. The tournament featured 291 wrestlers: 97 in Greco-Roman (GR), 98 in Freestyle (FS), and 96 in Women's Wrestling (WW).

A total of 26 national teams earned medals (GR – 13, FS – 13, WW – 12), and 49 teams accumulated points (GR – 30, FS – 31, WW – 27). In terms of medal success by style, the top-performing nations were Iran in both GR and FS (4 medals each) and Japan in WW (6 medals). Overall, Japan (11 medals), Iran (8 medals), and the USA (7 medals) emerged as the most successful nations across all styles. This highlights the continued global competitiveness of wrestling and the dominance of Asian teams in recent years.

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